

Global surgical systems: progress, gaps, and priorities for the next decade

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Our new Lancet Health Policy analysis¹ is the major comprehensive audit of surgical access since publication of the Lancet Commission on Global Surgery in 2015². These benchmarks should be viewed in context, since the severe constraints of the COVID-19 pandemic hampered progress. Without the efforts made so far, performance would have been even weaker. Low-income countries still perform fewer than 1000 operations per 100,000 population each year, one fifth of the benchmark set ten years ago². Postoperative death remains a major unsolved problem, now estimated at more than three million deaths annually, exceeding deaths from tuberculosis, malaria, and HIV/AIDS combined (figure 1)³. These figures should continue to force the global surgery community to rethink how it frames value, measures progress, and persuades governments to invest.

Figure 1: Global annual deaths 30 days after surgery versus major infectious diseases

The new analysis argues that surgery should be viewed as health-system infrastructure. A hospital able to repair a hernia today can typically also provide the oxygen, electricity, and sterilisation capacity required for a cross-

cutting range of other procedures, including caesarean section and trauma care. This systems view is reflected in World Health Assembly Resolution 68.15, which embeds emergency and essential surgical care within Universal Health Coverage⁴. The resolution, however, risks being seen financially competitive with other essential areas including vaccines, basic medications, and maternal care. Furthermore, surgery risks being downgraded within that resolution as global funding models change.

Moving away from a competitive view into a financially collaborative one is perhaps the only way to move forwards. For example, updated modelling in the Health Policy article shows that scaling a package of essential surgical cancer procedures in low- and middle-income countries could return productivity gains well above implementation costs⁵. Similar economic analyses for obstetrics and trauma are overdue and may help persuade health ministers to invest in core surgical services in the future.

Worldwide surgical data architecture has improved greatly over the last decade but remains fragile. Prospective, observational cohort studies have proved useful in even hard to reach areas, illustrated by data from district hospitals, including quality assurance of mesh inguinal hernia repair when supervision and supplies exist⁶. These granular data are more informative than aggregate procedure counts, yet the data infrastructure (spanning 3000 hospitals in 130 countries) is currently reliant on short-term funding. Without long-term support, this unique data network risks being lost through funding loss, pandemic shock, or war dominance.

Quality of surgery remains an unsolved and under-researched area. Surgical site infection after abdominal surgery is three times more frequent in low-income settings than in high-income settings⁶. Postoperative mortality rates remain unacceptably high, are higher in resource-limited hospitals, and randomised trials attempting to improve it are rare. The importance of this methodology was shown by a major international cohort study that addressed peri-operative SARS-CoV-2 infection and mortality at scale, drawing urgent attention to system resilience during the COVID pandemic^{7,8}. Research funders that claim surgery is a cross-cutting enabler must now support multicentre pragmatic trials and robust implementation studies.

Expansion cannot proceed without accounting for climate and equity. Health systems generate about 4% of global greenhouse emissions and operating theatres contribute a quarter of that total⁹. Reusable textiles, low-flow anaesthesia, and solar power are no longer demonstration projects and require funding for responsible expansion.

Equity gaps remain, with women and patients in the poorest quintiles receiving the fewest elective operations, despite equal or greater need. National surgical plans should therefore report outcomes by sex, age, wealth, and rural residence, mirroring approaches in maternal health.

Workforce shortage will determine success or failure of these plans. The global deficit of surgeons, anaesthetists, and obstetricians exceeds one million providers⁸. Regional training bodies such as the Colleges of Surgery of East, Central, and Southern Africa now graduate nearly a thousand surgeons a year, with most remaining in the region and representing a sustainable model².

Financing reform would address patient-level costs. Catastrophic expenditure pushes an estimated one in three households into financial hardship after surgery in low-income settings¹⁰. Affordable care packages need transparent fee schedules, insurance mechanisms, and social-protection schemes if utilisation is to rise once capacity exists. These may require innovative financial models as pressure on philanthropy, following sudden changes in global health funding, are extreme.

The new Health Policy article sets out an agenda for the next decade. First, measurement remains crucial, and should include procedure volume by urgency, thirty-day mortality, catastrophic expenditure, and carbon output. Second, hospital basics should be seen as critical building blocks for funding by governments; this includes reliable power, water, sterilisation, and resilient supply chains for mesh, antibiotics, blood, and anaesthetic drugs¹¹. Third, high quality clinical data and cost models will present ministries with credible estimates of productivity gains. Fourth, investment in people will expand regional training pipelines and embed data competence within curricula.

The Health Policy paper shifts global surgery from aspiration towards accountability, and from standalone to integrated into complete health systems. It reminds clinicians, researchers, and policy leaders that numerical targets without political traction will not deliver care at scale. Ten years after Global Surgery 2030, the field must move from counting gaps to closing them.

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References

1. Nepogodiev D, Picciochi M, Ademuyiwa A, et al. Surgical health policy 2025-35: strengthening essential services for tomorrow's needs. *Lancet*. 2025 Jul 14;S0140-6736(25)00985-7. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(25)00985-7.
2. Meara JG, Leather AJM, Hagander L, et al. Global Surgery 2030: evidence and solutions for achieving health, welfare, and economic development. *Lancet* 2015; 386: 569-624.
3. Nepogodiev D, Martin J, Biccari B, et al. Global burden of postoperative deaths: a modelling study. *Lancet* 2019; 393: 401-407.
4. World Health Assembly. Resolution 68.15: Strengthening emergency and essential surgical care and anaesthesia as a component of universal health coverage. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2015.

5. Alkire BC, Raykar NP, Shrime MG, et al. Global access to surgical care: a modelling study. *Lancet Glob Health* 2015; 3: e316-323.
6. GlobalSurg Collaborative. Surgical site infection after gastrointestinal surgery in high, middle and low income countries: a prospective cohort study. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2018; 18: 516-525.
7. CovidSurg Collaborative. Mortality and pulmonary complications in patients undergoing surgery with peri-operative SARS-CoV-2 infection: an international cohort study. *Lancet* 2020; 396: 27-38.
8. Weiser TG, Haynes AB, Molina G, et al. Size and distribution of the global volume of surgery in 2012. *Lancet Glob Health* 2016; 4: e567-575.
9. MacNeill AJ, Lillywhite R, Brown CJ. The carbon footprint of surgery: a systematic review. *Lancet Planet Health* 2017; 1: e381-388.
10. Shrime MG, Dare AJ, Alkire BC, et al. Catastrophic expenditure to pay for surgery worldwide: a modelling study. *Lancet Glob Health* 2015; 3: S38-S44.
11. Picciochi M, Agbeko AE, Agyei F. Variation of elective healthcare in West Africa: secondary analysis of an inguinal hernia international cohort study. *Impact Surg.* 2024; 1(4):145-53.
12. GAIT 2024 Collaborative Group. Generative Artificial Intelligence Transparency in scientific writing: the GAIT 2024 guidance. *Impact Surg* 2025; 2(1):6-11.